

METHODOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF TEACHING COMMUNICATION SKILLS

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***Annotation.** This article discusses the methodological aspects of teaching communication skills, emphasizing the importance of communicative activities in language teaching. Key elements include fostering a genuine desire to communicate, creating communicative purposes, focusing on language content, and minimizing artificial teacher intervention and simplified materials. Group work is highlighted as a critical form of realizing communication, with goals such as negotiation of input, fluency development, communication strategies, and content mastery. The theoretical framework underlines the importance of cooperative and communicative teaching for achieving communicative competence.*

***Keywords:** Communication skills, group work, communicative teaching, language learning, methodology, communicative competence, cooperative learning, fluency development, communication strategies.*

INTRODUCTION

Teaching communication skills is central to foreign language education, as it prepares learners to interact effectively in real-life contexts. This paper examines the methodological aspects of teaching communication skills, focusing on communicative activities that promote authentic language use. It also explores the role of group work as a tool for achieving communicative goals, emphasizing the

shift from traditional teacher-led approaches to learner-centered methods that prioritize interaction and practical application.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology emphasizes the principles of communicative teaching, which prioritize interaction and language use over form-focused instruction. Key aspects include:

1. **Creating a Desire to Communicate:** Activities are designed to involve real-world relevance, such as information or opinion gaps.
2. **Focusing on Content:** The emphasis is on meaningful exchanges rather than grammar drills.
3. **Encouraging Variety and Autonomy:** Learners are exposed to diverse language inputs without repetitive structures or teacher intervention.
4. **Group Work:** This is identified as a primary activity form, facilitating interaction, negotiation of meaning, fluency, and strategy development. Group work encourages learners to collaboratively achieve communicative goals and enhances their language proficiency through exposure and practice. The classroom CLT often takes the form of pair and group work requiring negotiation and cooperation between learners, fluency-based activities that encourage learners to develop their confidence, role-plays in which students practice and develop language functions, as well as judicious use of grammar and pronunciation focused activities such the aim of the communicative approach to language teaching is to focus on real conversations about real subjects so that communication is the engine of learning. This communication may lead to explanation, but that this in turn will lead to further communication approach is based on ten principles¹.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The discussion highlights the benefits of group work and communicative activities:

1. **Negotiation of Input:** Learners gain access to comprehensible language input

¹ Connery, B. A. Group Work and Collaborative Writing // Teaching at Davis, 2003, 14 (1), 2-4. (Publication of the Teaching Resources Center, University of California at Davis)

and opportunities to acquire new vocabulary and structures.

2. Exposure to New Language Items: Group work provides diverse linguistic input, promoting individualization and a conducive learning atmosphere.

3. Fluency Development: Repeated practice in interactive settings helps learners internalize language features and develop confidence.

4. Learning Communication Strategies: Group activities foster the use of strategies like clarifying meaning, managing conversations, and compensating for gaps in knowledge.

5. Content Integration: Communicative tasks enable learners to master both language skills and curriculum-related content.

The results indicate that group work, rooted in cooperative and communicative teaching principles, is effective in fostering communicative competence and addressing both language and content-learning goals. The approach pioneered by D. Hymes is now known as the ethnography of communication, has occurred regarding linguistic competence and communicative competence in the second and foreign language teaching literature, and scholars have found communicative competence as a superior model of language following D. Hymes' opposition to N. Chomsky's linguistic competence. This opposition has been adopted by those who seek new directions toward a communicative era by taking for granted the basic motives and the appropriateness of this opposition behind the development of communicative competence².

CONCLUSION

The methodological aspects of teaching communication skills highlight the significance of authentic, interactive, and learner-centered approaches in language education. Group work emerges as a versatile and effective strategy for enhancing language learning, fostering communication skills, and integrating curriculum content. By emphasizing cooperation and interaction, educators can create a dynamic learning environment that promotes both linguistic and cognitive

² Davies, N. F. Training fluency: An essential factor in language acquisition and use // RELC Journal, 2006, N6, pp.1-13

development, equipping learners with the skills needed for real-world communication. Grammatical competence is the ability to recognize and produce the distinctive grammatical structures of a language and to use them effectively in communication. competence as defined by Noam Chomsky would include phonological competence. of French need to learn to understand the different time references of sets of words such as je parlais, je parle, je parlerai, and to be able to make appropriate time reference when speaking or writing³

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³ Doff A. Teach English. - Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2005. - 286 p